

NDAC/LO/107
Mar 30, 1988

HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, VIa.

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A general outline of NDAC:s double star reduction process was given in a contribution at the INCA colloquium in Sitges, Jan 25-29, 1988 (S. Söderhjelm: 'Double star processing by NDAC'). In the work with a 'realistic' STDDBL-program, some important refinements and simplifications have been introduced, as described below in Sections 1 and 2. In Section 3, the astrometric results of a large number of test-runs are given, enabling an optimization of the weighting. In Section 4, the photometric results are studied, disclosing e.g. a colour-equation for the primary magnitudes. Section 5, finally, lists some points to be considered in the next report of this series.

1. The effective IFOV profile

In my old versions of the programs for known wide doubles (individual IFOV pointing), the 'effective' IFOV attenuation (for one star when pointing at the other) is a solution parameter. For wide multiples, several such attenuation factors might then be necessary, and to simplify, I later decided to use only a single 'scale-factor' (a), taking $f_{eff}(r) = f_{nom}(ar)$, where f_{nom} is the nominal IFOV profile. While testing this idea for doubles, (where the final result should be the same as with the old concept), I noted that the a -factor decreased quite regularly with the separation between the stars. This is indeed expected, because in the rapidly sloping wings of the IFOV-profile, the pointing uncertainty will introduce a bias towards larger f_{eff} (smaller a). Mathematically, f_{eff} is the (2-dimensional) convolution of f_{nom} with the (gaussian) pointing distribution. In the solution programs, one should therefore replace the nominal profile with f_{eff} . The a -factor should then be close to unity, serving as a test that the nominal profile and the assumed pointing spread has been suitably chosen.

In the present tests of this idea, I have calculated $f_{eff}(r, \sigma)$ by a simple Monte-Carlo technique. For a specified pointing spread (σ_F) and a specified nominal distance from the IFOV centre, I simply make some 1000 gaussian pointings and evaluate the mean and the spread in f_{eff} . The means are then fitted by a set of cubic splines, giving f_{eff} for $\sigma=1.5-3.5$ in steps of 0.5 arcsec. (Most simulations have $\sigma_F=2.5$ arcsec, and so far interpolation is linear in σ). The variances are similarly fitted, replacing the old 'wing' and 'peak' variances introduced in NDAC/LO/067, but in fact very similar to these numerically.

In STDDBL, then, the IFOV profile is taken as the spline function $f_{eff}(r, \sigma)$, and the normalized variances as a function $f_{var}(r, \sigma)$. Because $f_{eff}(0, \sigma)$ is now no longer equal to unity, the old weight-adjustment by increasing the assumed value for σ is no longer suitable. Instead, I have introduced a *varfac*-factor multiplying the calculated variances in the weighting, and one important goal of the simulations described below is to optimize *varfac*. Another minor improvement concerns the nominal r -values for the variance calculations. Before, I just used the 'ideal' pointings, letting e.g. $r = 0$ or $r = sep$ for a wide double. Now I use the difference between the actual and the *a priori* positions to give a statistically correct r . (The difference is usually less than the pointing σ , and it has therefore rather little effect on the solution results).

2. The mesh-search for the primary position

The search for a correct primary position has been so far performed in a 2-step process, with first 19, then 36 auxiliary mesh-points (cf. NDAC/LO/103). This works well, but it is somewhat difficult to extend for the cases with very bad *a priori* positions. A both simpler and more efficient technique has now been introduced. Firstly, the hexagonal mesh has been supplanted by a simpler circular one, consisting of $6m$ equidistant points on circles with radii $r_m = 1 + 0.9 * (m - 1)$, $m=1,2,\dots$ (cf. Fig. 1.). The advantages are the circular symmetry and the easy extension to arbitrary distances, while the disadvantage is the slightly larger 'minimum distance to a mesh-point' for some few points. For a hexagonal mesh with spacing g , the largest minimum is $g/\sqrt{3} = 0.577g$. For the circular mesh (with identical first 7 points), the corresponding value is about $0.65g$. (Another way to specify the efficiency is to give the percentage of random gaussian points falling more than $0.5g$ from a mesh-point. This fraction is 9.3% with a hexagonal grid, 10-11% with the circular one, depending on the gaussian σ).

Secondly, the solutions are no longer saved for some subset of the mesh-points (with subsequent selection of the one with minimum χ^2). Instead, a rather liberal limit $C\chi_a$ for S_a (= the χ^2 fit to the observations divided by the theoretical number of degrees of freedom), is specified in the '*a priori*' phase of the solutions. Any solution with $S_a < C\chi_a$ is repeated in the unconstrained 'final' mode. Often, this will indeed be the final solution, but if the normalized fit to the observations is unsatisfactory (as specified now by $S_f > C\chi_f$), the mesh-search is continued. One could use a mesh-size g small enough that any possible solution must be found, and just continue the search out to the largest conceivable distance from the *a priori* position. It will be more efficient however to again divide the search in two parts: First, a slightly larger g -value is used, out to a maximum distance that will include the large majority of *a priori* errors. The small fraction (<10%) of the systems with no solutions in this phase then either have an unusually large *a priori* error, or an unfortunate location far from a mesh-point. In either case, they will be picked up by the first-described procedure (small g , large number of mesh-points). Overall, this procedure is simpler to program than the old, it works for any reasonable *a priori* position error, and it is easy to 'fine-tune' to the real data.

3. Optimization of varfac

A program containing the 'core' of the final STDDBL has been written and run rather extensively on some existing simulated Case History Files. (The lacking parts are the input and output from the program which have to be specified further. The present interest is still the comparison of the solution parameters with the known true parameters for a wide variety of systems). The simulated doubles all have an *a priori* relative position error of 0.25 arcsec, and an *a priori* primary position error of 1.25 or 1.06 arcsec, thus an optimization of the g and $C\chi$ -parameters is not yet worthwhile. As 'standard' values I have used $g=0.70$ arcsec in 'phase one', $g=0.50$ arcsec in the subsequent 'follow up'-phase, this latter value being small enough that

no solution has failed completely. For $C\chi_a$ the value 50 has been found to be a good compromise for the closer doubles ($sep < 10$ arcsec, one pointing per system). For the wider pairs (with individual IDT pointings), 15 is a more reasonable value, otherwise one gets (for some reason) a too large number of 'false' *a priori* solutions. The 'final' solutions are mostly easy to pick out, but some care has to be given to the choice of $C\chi_f$, because the observed mean of S_f may differ somewhat from unity. (Mostly, $C\chi_f = 1.5-2.0$ is appropriate).

What I have tried to optimize is instead the *varfac* parameter. In my old experiments (NDAC/LO/067), I found a 40% increase of the assumed pointing σ to give the best weighting. This would correspond to $varfac=2$, but it appears now that such a large 'downweighting' may be excessive. To give a reliable answer, a large number of solutions (250 at each *varfac*) have been made with $varfac=0.5, 1.0, 1.5$ and 2.0, and standard astrometric 'rms'-results (as used in all my previous experiments) are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Mean rms-errors (mas) for different values of *varfac* for some series of runs with equal-magnitude systems (8.5+8.5) at low ecliptic latitude. Series A1-A3 (cf. NDAC/LO/103) are with single, A10-A30 with individual IDT-pointing. The *err*-column gives the statistical error in these means, (10-25 runs, 20-50 rms-values).

Ser	sep(")	varfac				err
		0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	
A1	0.4	1.70	1.68	1.67	1.66	0.10
A2	1.5	1.64	1.62	1.62	1.62	0.07
A3	10	1.72	1.76	1.80	1.82	0.10
A10	10	1.88	1.84	1.85	1.86	0.22
A15	15	2.34	2.27	2.26	2.25	0.20
A20	20	2.00	2.00	2.02	2.04	0.16
A25	25	1.68	1.66	1.66	1.68	0.12
A30	30	1.30	1.32	1.33	1.35	0.16
mean	-	1.75	1.74	1.75	1.75	-

Table 2. Mean rms-errors (mas) for different values of *varfac* for some series of runs with $dm=1.5$ systems (8.5+10.0) at low ecliptic latitude. Series B1-B3 are with single, B10-B30 with individual IDT-pointing. The *err*-columns gives the statistical error in these means, (10-25 runs).

Ser	sep(")	primary					secondary				
		0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	err	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	err
B1	0.4	1.28	1.29	1.30	1.31	0.16	5.09	4.98	4.92	4.88	0.51
B2	1.5	1.31	1.30	1.30	1.31	0.07	5.43	5.35	5.31	5.30	0.47
B3	10	1.24	1.24	1.26	1.27	0.07	4.17	4.09	4.11	4.16	0.33
B10	10	1.42	1.40	1.42	1.44	0.11	5.59	5.31	5.28	5.29	0.34
B15	15	1.39	1.32	1.31	1.31	0.12	4.95	4.74	4.65	4.64	0.55
B20	20	1.61	1.56	1.54	1.54	0.13	7.25	7.25	7.30	7.35	0.35
B25	25	1.32	1.32	1.34	1.36	0.12	4.47	4.77	4.96	5.06	0.62
B30	30	1.36	1.38	1.38	1.39	0.16	2.66	2.58	2.57	2.59	0.35
mean	-	1.33	1.32	1.33	1.34	-	4.93	4.86	4.85	4.86	-

The main conclusion from these data is that the exact value of *varfac* (in the range 1-2) has very little effect on the final accuracy of the solutions. From a practical point of view, a more important effect of the weighting is its influence on the formal mean errors of the solution parameters. This has been studied by forming the S_e -parameter defined in NDAC/LO/095 (squared sum of the actual over the formal error for the five astrometric parameters), which should ideally be χ^2 -distributed with 5 d.o.f.. An increase of *varfac* corresponds to an increase of the formal mean errors, and thus to a diminishing S_e , and it is useful to choose a *varfac* that gives a mean S_e close to 5.

In the present experiments, I have calculated Se_1 for the primary component, Se_r for the relative data (sec-pr). Due to the large statistical variations, it seems sufficient to give the observed means for either 50 'close' (sep=0.4, 1.5 arcsec) or 75 'wide' (sep=10-30 arcsec) systems. These data are given in Table 3.

Table 3a. Mean Se_1 -values (mean error of mean in parenthesis) as function of *varfac*. A and B series as defined before, close sep=0.4, 1.5 arcsec, wide sep=10-30 arcsec.

Ser	varfac			
	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0
A close	9.9(0.9)	8.5(0.8)	7.5(0.7)	6.8(0.6)
B close	8.8(0.7)	7.8(0.8)	7.0(0.7)	6.5(0.7)
A wide	8.4(0.6)	6.2(0.5)	5.1(0.4)	4.4(0.3)
B wide	8.7(0.5)	7.0(0.4)	6.1(0.4)	5.6(0.4)

Table 3b. Mean Se_r -values (mean error of mean in parenthesis) as function of *varfac*.

Ser	varfac			
	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0
A close	7.3(0.7)	6.3(0.6)	5.8(0.5)	5.3(0.5)
B close	10(1.1)	9.0(1.0)	8.0(0.9)	7.3(0.8)
A wide	7.1(0.7)	4.9(0.4)	3.9(0.3)	3.3(0.3)
B wide	6.8(0.7)	5.0(0.5)	4.1(0.4)	3.6(0.3)

For primary components, the Se_1 -values are rather independent of the magnitude difference (A- and B-series about equal), but the values are significantly higher for 'close' than for 'wide' systems. This same general trend holds also for the relative Se_r -values, and forming simply the grand means for 'wide' and for 'close' systems, *varfac*=1.5 gives the reasonable values $Se=4.8$ for the wide systems, $Se=7.1$ for the close ones. More runs are needed to refine the statistics, but *varfac*=1.5 is hereby adopted as a standard, which should give real errors mostly below 1.2 times the formal ones.

4. IFOV profile and magnitudes

The new IFOV-profile described in Section 1 does indeed give a value close to unity for the scale-factor *a*. The data from the 'wide' runs with individual pointing is summarized in Table 4. With only 10 runs per series, the observed standard deviations are in satisfactory agreement with the formal ones.

Table 4. Mean *a*-values (observed s.d. in parenthesis) with their formal mean errors (me), for the above A10-A30 and B10-B30 series.

Sep(")	A-ser		B-ser	
	<i>a</i>	me	<i>a</i>	me
10	0.989(0.012)	0.019	1.000(0.027)	0.022
15	1.001(0.004)	0.010	0.998(0.018)	0.011
20	1.003(0.004)	0.007	0.997(0.007)	0.008
25	1.006(0.005)	0.006	1.005(0.007)	0.007
30	1.003(0.010)	0.011	1.000(0.010)	0.010

So far, only the astrometric parameters have been considered. For each system, the solution gives also a primary magnitude and a magnitude difference, and it is of course interesting to see how well these are determined. Generally, the magnitude differences have errors close to the formal ones, as may be seen from Table 5. For the A-series (by symmetry), the mean $\Delta(\Delta m)$:s are very close to zero, but for the B-series with $\Delta m=1.5$, there are systematic shifts varying with the separation. These effects have to be studied further, over a greater range of Δm .

Table 5. Mean $d(dm)$ -values (obs standard deviation in parenthesis) with their formal mean errors, for the above A- and B-series.

Sep(")	A-ser		B-ser	
	$d(dm)$	me	$d(dm)$	me
0.4	0.000(0.012)	0.010	0.011(0.019)	0.018
1.5	0.000(0.008)	0.007	0.016(0.019)	0.016
10	0.000(0.010)	0.010	0.003(0.017)	0.017
10-20	-0.001(0.017)	0.015	0.019(0.036)	0.028
25-30	0.000(0.007)	0.009	-0.031(0.018)	0.019

If we look instead at the errors in the primary magnitudes, the observed spread is markedly larger than the formal mean errors. Here, however, the extra variance is completely explained as a colour effect. Figure 2 shows the error in the primary magnitude as function of the colour of the primary for 100 'close' doubles. (The A- and B-series give identical relations). The 'wide' systems again give a similar figure, but possibly with a small (0.01 mag) vertical shift. The explanation for this effect lies in the use in the solution programs of constant modulation coefficients (M1 and M2) defined for $(B-V)=0.5$. The simulation values are colour-dependent (cf. eq. 8 in NDAC/LO/066), decreasing by some 8% for an increase of unity in B-V. This decrease is interpreted by the solution program as a loss of intensity, in good quantitative agreement with the slope in Fig. 2. Because the relation is so tight, it will be easy to calibrate away after the reductions, and for the magnitudes it will *not* be necessary to know the colour in the reductions.

Fig. 2. Magnitude error vs colour for primary components

The question of colour-equations in the astrometry is of course more serious. In the present simulations, the CHF-files were derived assuming complete knowledge of the field-to-grid transformations, including the colour-dependence. Therefore, no colour-effects should be present, as seen e.g. in Fig 3., giving the parallax errors for the above 'close' systems. Because the grid-phase errors due to imperfectly known colours are always small (< 1 mas) and 'randomized' over the different FOV-passages, any effects in the final results should be very small.

Fig. 3. Parallax errors vs pr colour.

5. Further testing

The test-results summarized in Sections 3 and 4 above are encouraging, but there are several further points to consider:

1. For optimizing g and $C\chi$, the *a priori* primary and relative 'Input Catalogue' errors should be given realistic statistical distributions.
2. A larger variation over separations and magnitude differences should be used.
3. The colour-information used in the CHF-calibration should be degraded.
4. A realistic time-variation of the IDT-sensitivity should be introduced, and possibly also some doubles with variable components.

The results of such further tests have to be favourable before 'STDDBL' may be considered working, but the insights gained from such testing will certainly be helpful also in developing the other DS reduction programs.